

The **first** trans-continental **Networking Academy** for
African and European Digital Innovation Hubs.

D6.6 Electronic newsletter – First Release

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Executive Summary

Youthmakers Hub, with the contribution of all partners, has produced the first newsletter; more will follow, one every semester. The newsletter was circulated in an electronic format to the interested public through the Mailchimp platform, and it was also uploaded to the official project webpage (<https://africoneu.eu/newsletter/>). The first newsletter of the project was released and sent on 16th July 2021. A database with e-mails has been developed during the last months with all people subscribed to our newsletter. 165 people received the newsletter. Four main categories have been included in the newsletter: About the project, Opportunities & News, Participation in Events, and Completed AfriConEU activities.

The issue published illustrated the achievements reached during the reported period, both in terms of projects developments as well as peripheral activities, such as participation in external events. Given the importance of the newsletter, it has to be concise, avoid jargon, clarify, and make the final text attractive enough to make all kinds of readers want to find out more about the project.

[AfriConEU Newsletter #1 | July 2021](#)

AfriConEU Newsletter #1 | July 2021

Welcome to our very first **Newsletter!** We're glad you're here. Twice a year, we'll be informing you about AfriConEU's progress and updates.

Let's get started!

About the project

This is AfriConEU

AfriConEU is an [Horizon 2020 project](#) aspiring to create the first trans-Continental Networking Academy to support African and European Digital Innovation Hubs in capacity building, knowledge sharing, networking, joint projects, and venture development.

The project's partners

We are 11 partners representing DIHs, Universities, Consultancies, and CSOs from 5 European and 4 African countries supporting the collaboration between EU and African DIHs to strengthen a common EU-Africa innovation and Start-up ecosystem.

Opportunities & News

Agrifood Cooperation Platform | Join other DIHs around the world

The online platform provided by the [DIH AGRIFOOD](#) serves the “AfriConEU Networking Academy” in connecting organizations in the agri-food sector from both continents. We invite Digital Innovation Hubs to register on the platform.

To join, [click here](#).

AfriConEU in the Press

The project essentially strengthens the digital innovation ecosystems in Africa by targeting existing Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) and supporting them through capacity building and networking activities. The Consortium launched the project on the 1st of February 2021, and it will last for 36 months until the 31st of January 2024.

→ [Read more](#)

Participation in Events

AfriConEU at the Emerging Valley | April 7th & 8th, 2021

Our team participated in the [Emerging Valley Online Edition](#). We interacted with the event's speakers, startups, Tech Hubs, and Investors from Africa and Europe, creating networks for potential collaborations in a dynamic and innovative business ecosystem.

→ [Read more](#)

AfriConEU at the AEIP Final Conference | June 29th & 30th, 2021

On 29th and 30th of June 2021, we took part in the Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership's final conference: "[Building Sustainable Partnerships with Enrich in Africa & beyond](#)", presenting the project. In addition, we connected with similar initiatives and discussed future synergies. → [Read more](#)

Completed AfriConEU Activities

AfriConEU Virtual Roundtables: Building Resilient African Digital Economies post-COVID with a focus on West and East Africa

Digital technologies have captured our attention and boosted certain sections of our economies. But has this transformation benefited everyone? Are we all ready to take the opportunities that digitalization has brought with it? Specifically, how has this 'new normal' impacted African startups, SMEs, and entrepreneurs? Let's look at what ATBN, in collaboration with [HapaSpace](#), [Emerging Communities Africa](#), [Outbox](#), and [Buni Innovation Hub](#), organized during the last few months. Check below.